

What, where, and how much? Downscaling spatial, sectoral, global economic activity

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Summary

The distribution of economic activity over space is a central question in economic geography, which can inform policies targeting sustainable development and regional economic growth, as well as assessing indirect losses from disruptions in the context of climate risk assessment. In this work, we develop a novel and flexible method applying Bayesian hierarchical modelling to produce estimates of economic activity at high spatial and sectoral resolution, based on global, open data.

KEYWORDS: spatial economics, downscaling, bayesian modelling

How economic activity in different sectors is distributed across space is a central question in economic geography (Peet 1969). In a globalised world, highly connected through supply chain networks supporting trade in goods across many sectors of the economy, there is a need to understand the impacts of localised changes in, or disruption to, sectoral production around the world, in order to analyse systemic resilience and the potential for wide, indirect impacts (Levermann 2014).

Despite various survey and modelling efforts, globally consistent datasets describing economic activity, in terms of output (sectoral production) or gross value added, are available only at national or regional scales (World Bank 2024; Wenz et al. 2023), or at fine spatial resolution only as estimates of aggregate gross domestic product or productivity (Kummu et al. 2018), or for a few sub-sectors of the economy, particularly in agriculture (Ru et al. 2023).

These limitations are particularly acute in developing and rapidly urbanizing regions, including low- and middle-income countries in Africa and Asia, where detailed data are often scarce despite these areas accounting for a growing share of global economic activity, infrastructure development and population growth. In the case of analysing disruption from extreme climate events, these also have a disproportionately greater impact on communities and the economy in developing countries (Hallegatte et al. 2017).

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To address this gap and pave the way for a granular understanding of the spatial and sectoral distribution of economic activity around the globe, this work introduces a flexible method, relying on global, open data, which produces high resolution estimates of sectoral distribution and economic output in space.

1 Methods

The method involves three main steps:

- **Data Collection and Preprocessing:** data are downloaded, transformed into consistent file formats, and allocated to spatial units, providing proxies, priors and constraints for the modelling.
- **Downscaling:** a Bayesian hierarchical model integrates geospatial variables (e.g., population density, infrastructure distribution, night-time light emissions, and land use classifications) and coarse-resolution constraints on spatial, sectoral economic activity.
- **Validation:** datasets representing aggregations of spatial, sectoral activity, some with limited geographical coverage, are used to validate our downscaled economic distributions.

There are multiple sources for global data covering different sectors of economic activity and physical features, available at different resolutions, covering different time periods, and provided in different formats and coordinate systems.

Inputs are taken from: multi-regional input-output tables for national, sectoral production (Lenzen et al. 2017a), non-residential built-up area (European Commission. Joint Research Centre. 2023), and points of interest and land use from Overture Maps¹ and OpenStreetMap (OpenStreetMap contributors 2017).

Validation data sets include: combined national/sub-national sectoral value added from the World Development Indicators (World Bank 2024), the CIA World Factbook² and Wenz et al. (2023) and the US Bureau of Economic Analysis³ county level economic activity.

Data is projected onto the H3 grid⁴. Raster data cell centroids are projected onto H3 at a resolution higher than the raster cell size, then a Voronoi tessellation fills any gaps in the H3 grid. Points are allocated directly to their nearest H3 cell. Polygons are allocated to all contained H3 cells. The resolution for projection of vector features is chosen to cover the equivalent of a small building block, ≈ 100 meters.

The multi-faceted nature of the problem, which takes into account prior knowledge on the spatial locations, general law of distribution of economic output, as well as expert knowledge on certain sectors naturally fits into a Bayesian framework. A Bayesian hierarchical method (Song et al. 2014) allows us to model complex phenomena relying both on prior information, which can be obtained

¹<https://overturemaps.org/>

²<https://www.cia.gov/the-world-factbook/>

³<https://www.bea.gov/>

⁴<https://h3geo.org/>

by the modeller from heterogeneous sources, but also integrate a stochastic approach to parameter exploration. The modelling step is realised by running a Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) process and results in a posterior distribution. The output of this process incorporates our prior beliefs and adjusts them based on likelihoods given observed data.

The core of the model can be summarised as follows:

$$\mathbf{W} = \text{SkewNormal}(\mu, \kappa)$$

$$\mathbf{Y} = \text{LogNormal}(\mathbf{W} * \mathbf{X}, \sigma)$$

Where W is the matrix of econometric weights for which the mean (μ) and standard deviation (κ) are fixed using available information on the input proxy data and the constraints, X is a matrix of proxy variables index representing rescaled and normalised input proxy data, Y is a matrix containing per sector per location output samples, σ is the uncertainty, taken as a fixed fraction of the lognormal mean. This sampling is performed under the following constraints:

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{G}_\lambda, j \in \mathcal{S}_\zeta} \mathbf{Y}_{ij} = \mathcal{V}^{(\lambda\zeta)}$$

where \mathcal{G}_λ is a unit of the geographical constraint, \mathcal{S}_ζ is a unit of the sectoral constraint, and $\mathcal{V}^{(\lambda\zeta)}$ is the corresponding region and sector aggregated value at the resolution of the constraint.

2 Results

We model economic output (production) at an ISIC Section (letter level) sectoral resolution, and at a spatial resolution on a grid of hexagonal cells of diameter $\approx 10\text{km}$ down to $\approx 0.5\text{km}$. Figure 1 shows an example output.

3 Validation and limitations

The downscaling problem is under-specified. We infer a metric of production at a combined sectoral and spatial resolution higher than any reported statistics or accounts with consistent and complete coverage. As the primary method for validation, in various geographical contexts, we aggregate the modelled outputs by sector, space, or both, and compare them with other sources. As a secondary method, we propose to conduct spot-check comparisons of a subset of sectors with a high concentration of activity in well-reported sites, such as petrochemicals or steel manufacturing.

Figure 2 shows an example of the primary validation routine made with model output for Korea and Singapore compared with GDP (all-sector) data from Kummu et al. (2018) at $\approx 1\text{km}$ spatial resolution. Some notable differences are attributed to the downscaling assumption, in our cases relying on industrial points of interests, while Kummu et al. (2018) rely on high resolution population

Figure 1: Global downscaled mining output. Mining areas were taken from Maus et al. (2020) and OpenStreetMap contributors (2017); Mining production values were aggregated from Lenzen et al. (2017b)

grids. As a result, the non-populated industrial clusters in the south west of Singapore receive significantly more output in our model.

Figure 2: Log scaled normalised residuals between Kummu et al. (2018) and the BHM outputs.

4 Conclusions

In this work, we propose a novel and flexible method capable of producing estimates of economic activity at high spatial and sectoral resolution. This approach will accommodate improvements and adjustments as new data sets become available, or in application to more restricted geographical contexts with greater data availability, such as the UK.

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⁵<https://devtracker.fcdo.gov.uk/programme/GB-GOV-1-300125/summary>

Biographies

Ivann Schlosser is a Research Associate, working to combine and analyse global data sets of human economic activity, developing and publishing open source software for geospatial applications and modelling.

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Raghav Pant is a Senior Research Associate leading risk and resilience analysis research teams and specialising in evidence-based systems analysis across infrastructure sectors, including regional-scale multi-modal transport network risks and resilience to evaluate and prioritize climate adaptation investments.

Jim Hall FREng FRS is Professor of Climate and Environmental Risks, leading a research group which is at the forefront of risk analysis of climatic extremes and their impacts on infrastructure networks and economic systems, from local to global scales.

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